

Renewing biodiversity through
a people-in-nature approach

ExCASES Mission

The Future of Biodiversity Renewal

University
of Exeter

National Trust

Natural
Environment
Research Council

The Future of Biodiversity Renewal

An ExCASES Mission

ExCASES is part of the RENEW project – a Natural Environment Research Council (NERC) funded partnership between the University of Exeter and the National Trust that takes a ‘people-in-nature’ approach to address the challenges of biodiversity renewal. ExCASES undertakes agile research (called ‘missions’), on pressing biodiversity renewal issues, collaborating across disciplines and sectors. Missions aim to create impactful outputs for real change by undertaking original research, participatory processes, and/or synthesising existing knowledge for new audiences.

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The Future of Biodiversity Renewal

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1. The Future of Biodiversity Renewal: mission process

This mission undertook a process which sought to uncover the diversity of values, worldviews and understandings which shape multistakeholder aspirations for 'biodiversity renewal', with a focus on the RENEW research community and project partners (Figure 1). Our approach included use of the new [Restoration Partnership Development Toolkit](#) (RPDT), designed by academics at the University of Edinburgh and University of Cambridge. This elicits and then facilitates deliberation on a range of stakeholder perspectives about important areas within contemporary conservation discourse, practices and aspirations. The deliberative elements were held at the RENEW Biodiversity Parliament 2024 - the project's [annual meeting](#) that brings together researchers, partners, and support staff from the RENEW community to connect, reflect on progress, and explore the challenges and opportunities for biodiversity renewal (see Box 1). We anticipated this holistic process would help participants to understand each other's points of view and contribute to fairer and more effective biodiversity renewal practices, strategies and policies.

Figure 1 Diagram of The Future of Biodiversity Renewal mission process.

Using the RPDT, everyone in the RENEW community (e.g., project academics, support staff, PhD students, and partner organisation representatives) was invited to participate in an online survey, where they were asked to respond to a series of 40 statements using a Likert scale from strongly agree (5) to strongly disagree (1) to measure their attitudes and perceptions. Concepts and terminology that respondents might have been unfamiliar with were given short definitions. The statements were organised across five themes:

1. Decision making, finance, justice and equity
2. Relationships and relational values
3. Land use, farming, and food systems
4. Resilient and functioning ecosystems
5. Conservation approaches

The survey data (from 55 participants) was fed into the RPDT analysis app to generate visual outputs displaying the levels of agreement across participants towards the statements (Figure 2; levels of agreement), and levels of consensus across responses. These visualisations were used at the RENEW Biodiversity Parliament 2024 to stimulate facilitated discussions which explored:

- Where and why do people agree and disagree?
- Can participants reach consensus on responses to emergent biodiversity issues?
- Where are the sticking points/frictions within and between the five themes?
- What are parliament attendees' collective visions and aspirations for biodiversity renewal?
- Where there are diverging opinions and priorities, how might people from different sectors work better together to achieve mutual objectives?
- When and how is plurality useful?

Box 1: RENEW Biodiversity Parliament 2024

The RENEW Biodiversity Parliament 2024 was held in November at the London Wetland Centre over two half days. It was carefully planned by the RENEW Secretariat and ExCASES team in a way which supported the Future of Biodiversity mission aims and objectives. This included using a space that was also a centre for urban wildlife, starting each day with three provocations by external speakers, and evening entertainment that enabled more informal discussion and networking. To identify the external speakers, the Parliament organisers gathered recommendations from across the RENEW teams to create a long list of people from a broad range of backgrounds, disciplines and expertise who could bring novel insights and perspectives on the five themes of the survey. These served as thought-provoking inputs that enlivened the survey discussions which followed. The six speakers shared provocations from their work in ecology, farming, activism, law, conservation and Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI). The provocateurs and their roles, organisations, and talk titles are listed below in order of presentation:

James Bullock: Ecologist at the UK Centre for Ecology & Hydrology
Survival ecology and conservation in an uncertain future

Jyoti Fernandes: Smallholder farmer and Co-Founder of the Land Workers Alliance
Agroecological food webs across the world for global food and biodiversity

Dan Raven Ellison: Chief Exploration Officer at Slow Ways and Founder of National Park Cities
Re-imagining biodiversity - what if we made more city's National Park Cities?

Naomi Oakley: Organic farmer and Principal Specialist at Natural England
Upland farming – putting nature first

Paul Powlesland: Lawyer and Co-Founder of Lawyers for Nature
Towards rights of nature and guardianship

Louisa Adjoa Parker: Writer, Poet and EDI Consultant
Poetry as Reconnection - Self, Place, and Nature

2. Survey highlights

The RPDT highlighted areas of consensus and divergence around the statements. This formed the basis for discussion during the activities at the Parliament. At the start, to support reflection and dialogue, the ExCASES team provided an overview of the survey data for workshop participants, making the following observations:

1

Areas of agreement

There was **greatest agreement** with the following statements (mean Likert rating over 4, on a scale of 1-5):

- Public policy decisions should be obliged to consider by law the interests of future generations across the UK
- Local communities should have a direct say in decisions affecting their local environment
- An unequal distribution of decision-making power and resources has a negative impact on environmental outcomes
- Nature-friendly farming makes a meaningful contribution to domestic food security
- What landscapes deliver for biodiversity is more important than how they look

2

Areas of disagreement

Greatest disagreement was generated by the following statements (mean Likert rating below 2.5, on a scale of 1-5):

- Greater public access to land will negatively impact biodiversity renewal efforts
- It is better to have a high abundance of a few species than a low abundance of lots of different species
- Environmental damage can be justifiable if it protects economic interests
- It is more important to prioritise areas of high biodiversity abroad than the depleted biodiversity of the UK

3

Areas of neutrality or uncertainty

Statements generating the **highest level of neutrality/uncertainty** (over 50% of participants reporting 'neither agree nor disagree') were:

- Livestock grazing should play a major role in biodiversity renewal in the UK
- When looking after biodiversity, local knowledge is more valuable than scientific evidence
- Biodiversity renewal should include the intentional movement of species by people

Figure 2: The 40 survey statements organised in order of most to least agreement

Key ■ Strongly Disagree ■ Disagree ■ Neither Agree or Disagree ■ Agree ■ Strongly Agree

Figure 2: The 40 survey statements organised in order of most to least agreement

Key ■ Strongly Disagree ■ Disagree ■ Neither Agree or Disagree ■ Agree ■ Strongly Agree

Figure 2: The 40 survey statements organised in order of most to least agreement

Key ■ Strongly Disagree ■ Disagree ■ Neither Agree or Disagree ■ Agree ■ Strongly Agree

3. Participants' reflections

Participants expressed a range of reservations about the survey methodology. Some thought it was not robust enough and lacked statistical power (noting the small sample size), while other participants advocated a more qualitative approach (e.g. allowing contextualised responses). Some participants felt unqualified to give an informed response to certain statements, especially those containing unfamiliar concepts or a high degree of ambiguity.

By the end of the workshops, however, there was greater appreciation for the use of the survey as a tool to guide deliberations, and more confidence in the methodological process when experienced in its entirety. Participants reported that:

- Some survey results were unsurprising and, in several cases, unlikely to be representative of the UK public more broadly. This may reflect a bias in statement wording and framing, as well as many participants' inherent alignment with biodiversity conservation.
- Discussions around the statements were useful in supporting collective thinking about how to navigate and accommodate different viewpoints, and as anchor points for visioning solutions within RENEW and beyond.
- Convening RENEW members and project partners in a shared, facilitated space enabled people to engage with alternative perspectives and contextualise their own responses – supporting an empathic consideration of different perspectives.
- The workshops and provocations were a welcome opportunity for reflexivity, prompting participants to critically reflect on their personal interactions with nature, and how they advocate for nature and people within their organisations
- There was interest from participants in applying the concepts ExCASES and provocateurs had introduced to their own work, including utilising the RPDT.

ExCASES reflections:

It was interesting to see how, despite the variety of reflections on the survey before the workshops, by the end, participants from a range of disciplinary and professional backgrounds agreed that it was a useful framework around which to begin more in-depth discussions. It may be helpful for other users of the RPDT, and similar mixed-method participatory processes, to be aware of this participant 'journey'/progression and to not be discouraged when faced with critique about the initial, survey-based element of the process.

4. Key findings

Data from the workshops was recorded by facilitators in written form on flipchart paper and by audio recordings of plenary discussions. The data was transcribed and analysed using inductive thematic analysis to identify emergent themes. The emergent themes are reported in this section, with reflections from the ExCASES team.

4.1. Paradigm shift: ecological resilience and functioning ecosystems

Moving from a species-centric to ecosystems-resilience approach was an important conceptual shift in mindset for several partner organisations and workshop participants. Some key points included:

- There is a need to work out how this shift can be achieved in practice; in particular, what 'success' might look like and how it could be defined and measured.
- The objectives of futureproofing and 'restoring' ecosystems can sometimes seem contradictory but are often complementary.
- A hybrid approach to conservation that incorporates elements of 'survival ecology' (an adaptive, forward-looking strategy for sustaining biodiversity and ecosystem function amid inevitable environmental change) alongside more traditional methods will help to transition practices during uncertain times.
- People are sometimes hindered by shifting baseline syndrome (where the conditions we are born into and are familiar with are perceived as the norm leading to a gradual acceptance of environmental degradation over time) and a scarcity mindset (a way of thinking which focusses on what we lack or are missing).
- We need to be much bolder in our collective ambitions for nature. We shouldn't make a choice between abundance and diversity but aim for both.
- Questions remain about knock-on impacts and potential unintended consequences of novel approaches, e.g., what if outcomes from a more 'hands off' approach negatively impacted the conservation imperative for particular species, habitats, and people's livelihoods?
- To facilitate a shift towards an ecosystems-resilience and landscape-scale approach, we need to share new stories and narratives. A 'species lens', however, might still be useful to reach certain audiences.

ExCASES reflections:

The concept of survival ecology, mentioned in both the survey statements and provocations, was clearly thought-provoking to participants of the Parliament. Further work and research are required to explore what this approach looks like in practice. It would also be useful to identify the risks and opportunities for a selection of scenarios compared to current approaches.

4.2. Guardianship and rights of nature

Rights of nature and guardianship were unfamiliar concepts for many participants. The idea of guardianship was positively received and recognised as potentially powerful for re-imagining people's relationships with nature. Participants appreciated the provocations about guardianship and rights of nature, and discussed the following:

- Without rights, nature cannot be adequately protected from direct and indirect harm.
- Whilst there was an intuitive understanding that nature does and should have rights, applying this in specific scenarios is challenging. For example, a suggestion that the felling of the Sycamore Gap tree constituted murder was deeply uncomfortable for some people.
- Strong emotions and values underpin perceptions of whether nature has inherent rights, or not.
- Communicating the concepts of guardianship and rights of nature to a broad range of people and policy makers is challenging.
- Guardianship has the potential to give people a valued role within society and their local environment. RENEW could encourage this within partner organisations by, for example, contributing to the development of a national framework.
- An 'ecological extension service' (similar to agricultural extension services in other parts of the world which advise on farming) could provide support for landowners, managers and citizens interested in guardianship or nature restoration more broadly.

ExCASES reflections:

Guardianship could play a pivotal role in reimagining the relationship between people and nature by empowering individuals and communities to connect with, protect, and defend local environments. Whilst participants agree that nature should have rights, they diverge on the extent and practical implications of ascribing rights to nature. To move beyond philosophical debate, there is a need for plausible examples of how guardianship works in practice and how rights of nature could operate within the UK's existing legal framework.

4.3. Knowledge, data and evidence

There was consensus that decision-making should be evidence-based. However, there were various interpretations of what constituted valid evidence, with issues around access and scaling, and divergence over prioritisation. Participants noted that:

- Evidence should be generated and shared with transparency (there is some uncertainty about how to achieve this), and ‘experts’ should seek regular ‘reality checks’ about evidence needs from different stakeholders.
- There is an ongoing tension around balancing aesthetic or values-based preferences with scientific evidence in decision-making (this is discussed further in 4.5)
- There are unknowns associated with ambitious, experimental, and seminal approaches. In these cases, it is important to ask:
 - **Is theory enough in lieu of evidence?**
 - **How do we initiate novel approaches which lack comparatives or a foundation of evidence?**
- Investment drives innovation, however, novel approaches often lack metrics and measurements against which to gauge success and justify investment.
- Deciding what counts as ‘evidence’ is political. Evidence can be biased, so careful consideration is needed when choices are made that involve trade-offs.

ExCASES reflections:

Where robust evidence exists, it should drive biodiversity renewal objectives. In lieu of this – for example, when trialing novel approaches – we need processes that allow us to deliberately appraise perceived risk and reward, without opportunities being dismissed out of hand simply for lacking evidence. These processes must meaningfully involve affected stakeholders. Given the potential for bias, portfolios of evidence should incorporate knowledge from multiple disciplines, social and political considerations, and experiential knowledge.

4.4. Environmental and social justice

Greater consideration needs to be given to fairness and systems of access. However, navigating unequal distributions of power is complex. During discussions, there were some notable areas of agreement:

- Communities should have a direct say in decisions affecting their local environment.
- In practice, however, community and public perspectives are often only taken seriously when they align with those of decision-makers and 'experts'.
- Instead of applying a 'public deficit model' (providing more information and 'educating' publics to bring their views in line), organisations should authentically engage with communities. This would increase their awareness of the different factors that influence people's views (e.g., values, experience, and epistemology) which could then inform organisational decisions.
- When electoral and representational politics fail, people choose direct action. As one participant reflected, "Direct action is where the community speaks"; indeed, they are provocations.
- The interests of future generations should have legal standing in land use decision-making. There is precedence in the Welsh 'Wellbeing of Future Generations Act' which could be replicated in other devolved nations. However, policy makers may be cautious or reluctant about a legal obligation given the potential loss of future opportunities e.g., resource/land use options, and different responses to emerging economic and political factors.
- There are individuals, institutions and corporations that have vested interests in activities which are harmful to biodiversity and society who also have strong influencing power within policy spaces. This undermines efforts that seek environmental and social justice.

4.4. Environmental and social justice cont

Overall, this theme was characterised by unanswered, multidimensional questions:

- Which people and species are being excluded from natural spaces? Why is this happening? How are these decisions made and justified?
- How do decision makers balance the needs of people when they compromise the survival of other non-human species? Similarly, how are the potentially contradictory needs of different people, especially more marginalised groups, prioritised?
- How can conservationists and others working towards biodiversity renewal and environmental justice interrupt the political influence of harmful corporations?
- Do the conservation and scientific communities need to be more radical to push for change? Or are these disciplines apprehensive about engaging in radical political change in case it threatens personal comfort, job security, and relative privilege?

ExCASES reflections:

Representation of the rights of future generations in decision making processes was strongly supported. Participants reflected that support for the concept was a 'no brainer' in principle, but enshrining the rights of future generations in law would be a substantive challenge. Given the precedent set by the Wellbeing of Future Generations Act in Cymru (Wales), there is certainly an opportunity for appraisal of these challenges, exploring how the concept might translate to other devolved regions of the UK. Other aspects of this theme are less conclusive, raising questions rather than answering them. These could be helpful checkpoints for RENEW practitioners and academics alike to consider in their work. As one provocateur pointed out, continuing to ask difficult questions can be a catalyst for finding solutions.

4.5. Creating meaningful connections with nature and 'sense of place'

Maintaining a sense of meaning and identity for places undergoing change is important. Landscapes are layered with histories and cultural anchor points. To cultivate and protect emotional connections between people and land, it's important to retain meaning and distinctiveness for communities and visitors - not to try and jump from one state to another without a continuity of narrative. Key points from group discussions included:

- Navigating the interplay between cultural history, sense of place, and shifting baselines with biodiversity renewal is a sensitive, complex challenge. Particularly when traditional land uses (e.g., rearing and shooting pheasants) conflict with some conservation objectives.
- The appearance of landscapes is closely linked with identity, sense of place, and how they make you feel. Biodiversity renewal should utilise contextual interpretations of landscape. For example, in some places this could involve a shift in emphasis from what is 'seen' (negative perceptions of scrub vegetation) to what is 'experienced' (the songs of bird species that select scrub habitats).
- Cultural considerations and perspectives are important; for example, an overgrown public space could be seen as deliberately regenerative and biodiversity-rich to some, but overgrown, neglected and unsafe to others. This will depend on the community context and a person's values, experiences and cultural background.
- As in section 4.3, there is sometimes a conflict between scientific evidence and other forms of meaning-making (e.g., experiential, emotional, local ecological knowledge etc.) which can present challenges in decision-making spaces.

ExCASES reflections:

We need to be ambitious and aspirational towards biodiversity renewal objectives. In some cases, this may involve re-imagining landscapes and embracing uncertain outcomes. There is a challenge here in transition: to foster new narratives around landscape and senses of place that honour both human, cultural connections, and the beauty and ecological roles of non-human life. The concept of guardianship could be powerful in this transition. Working with the tension between scientific evidence and other forms of meaning-making, rather than glossing over differences, will be crucial. Different worldviews could be usefully integrated to create more sensitive, compassionate, and durable solutions. This is possible through effective facilitation that enables different perspectives to be better understood and valued.

4.6. Environmental governance

Better processes need to be developed which make space for constructive disagreement, facilitate integration of different values and knowledges (see 4.5), and balance evidence with equity. These will enable the negotiation of solutions that are recognised as democratically robust and fair, even if some people may not explicitly support or agree with the outcome. Other key points were:

- Engendering an emotional connection between people and nature, whilst important, can cause tension when implementing management decisions that cause harm e.g., the lethal control of wildlife.
- Conservation and land management decision-makers have a responsibility to ensure that decision-making processes are transparent, inclusive and evidence-based.
- Spatial and temporal exclusion, permit-based or smaller exclusion sites, and zoning might be necessary to effectively protect some species and habitats
- The conservation community needs to better understand how and why people make choices, and particularly what limits choice (e.g., financial and social factors, structural barriers, technological and institutional 'lock-ins', etc.).
- Co-creation should become the norm for decision making, particularly at local scales.
- There are often systemic reasons for policy failure, for example, policy change and efficacy can be disrupted by political cycles. When policy fails, it is important to acknowledge and understand why to improve future design and build trust.
- A multi-level governance approach may be instructive in helping to reconcile the dilemma of scaling. While not all projects can be scaled up, when appropriate, actors could start by scaling to the next level that feels workable and build vertically or horizontally from there.
- Gradual scaling could connect different efforts and leverage collective power incrementally, e.g., with respect to guardianship, this could take place at the increasing scale of, say, a river, catchment, region, or nation.

4.6. Environmental governance cont

As with section 4.4, there are some challenging outstanding questions associated with the theme of environmental governance:

- Who, for example, decides which species to protect and which to lethally control?
- Who decides who or what 'belongs' in different spaces, and who or what doesn't?
- Does a tendency in conservation to 'groupthink', and to search for silver bullet solutions, derail more subtle, nuanced, local, and contextually-relevant solutions?

ExCASES reflections:

These questions orientate around who has the power to make decisions, which provoked some critical self-reflection for participants and require deeper consideration at organisational levels. The ExCASES report '[Who decides for nature](#)' provides a deep dive into some of these topics. Taking lessons from innovative deliberative and participatory public engagement processes, the report makes recommendations for how to embed democratic governance within the nature sector, to support more inclusive and effective decision-making, and positive outcomes for biodiversity renewal.

4.7. Language and Communication

There were extensive discussions about how the framings and language used in the survey statements provoked different levels of emotive response (e.g., environmental 'damage,' economic 'interests,' 'traditional' approaches, interpretations of 'wild'). Participants felt that, as a result, their responses to some statements were more emotionally-charged than others – particularly for statements outside their technical expertise or understanding. Participants highlighted:

- 'Wildness' is a subjective and constructed concept, with questionable ecological relevance in the UK. It can be powerfully emotive: inspiring for some people, but a source of fear for others.
- Communicating an aspiration for nature-rich landscapes, whilst navigating the complexities of people's views towards the concept of 'wild', is challenging.
- Narratives around landscape need to change to bring local communities along with emergent visions of biodiversity renewal, e.g., redefining 'beauty' and 'wild', which are ultimately social constructs.

ExCASES reflections:

The world is storied: we can use language that captures a multitude of imaginations in support of biodiversity renewal. The language that we use affects how people receive and understand information and can support or inhibit openness to interventions. In light of participants' reflections that un-emotive/scientific language can limit the impact of messaging and alienate people, we need to take care to use accessible and context-appropriate wording in disseminating findings and recommendations.

4.8. Working across disciplines and sectors

Participants' disciplinary and professional backgrounds/roles shape the way they understand problems and identify solutions in relation to biodiversity renewal. This played out in the workshop discussions too. Some key points were:

- There is a spectrum of perspectives ranging from those who believe interdisciplinarity can 'just be done', and those who find it an insurmountable challenge.
- A shift from interdisciplinary (working across academic disciplines) to transdisciplinary (working across academic and non-academic disciplines and practices) work can be facilitated by academics engaging more directly with practitioners, focusing on what works on the ground.
- Many practitioners, however, do not use the words interdisciplinary or transdisciplinary outside of joint academic research projects.
- Workshop activities provided a rare environment for participants to consider biodiversity renewal from different thematic, disciplinary, spatial, and temporal perspectives. This was both a sobering reality check about the extent of disagreement or differing interpretations of the survey statements, and an opportunity to cultivate future collaboration.
- Diverse approaches, methods and philosophies can co-exist if they contribute to an explicit, overarching objective with clearly articulated goals.

ExCASES reflections:

The involvement of people from varied disciplines and roles resulted in discussions that were sometimes insightful and fruitful and, at other times, uncomfortable and challenging. It was interesting to observe this dynamic at the workshops, as it reflected what happens in broader biodiversity renewal contexts. People can feel confused by the concepts of inter- or transdisciplinarity but tend to acknowledge the benefits and opportunities they offer in practice. 'Learning through doing', therefore, appears to be the best way forward. Our experiences from conducting missions so far suggest that outcomes are usually enriched by integrating inputs from a diverse range of disciplines and stakeholders. Plurality should, therefore, be embraced. This can be supported by greater collaboration between academics and practitioners to help ensure that research is grounded in real-world contexts and focused on approaches that are effective and readily actionable.

5. Future directions

5.1. Visions for Biodiversity Renewal

The final activity at the Biodiversity Parliament invited participants to create aspirational visions for each of the five themes covered in the workshop discussions. These groupwork discussions have been written up and shared in the Appendix. The visions were not intended to be detailed, but to encourage forward-thinking ideas around how we might collaborate more effectively for more ambitious biodiversity renewal. They do not represent RENEW positions, but hopefully provide stimulus for further reflection and inspiration. There was a surprising degree of consensus. Where disagreement remained, it pertained mostly to socio-economic and political dimensions.

Weaving through the five visions, five threads could act as critical unifiers between stakeholders from wide-ranging sectors, disciplines and backgrounds as we work together for biodiversity renewal. These threads and their priorities are:

- 1 Decision-making processes: who is involved and how?**
Priorities: negotiating outcomes that are perceived and accepted to be fair; integration and balancing of different knowledges.

- 2 Evidence: whose evidence and how is it created?**
Priorities: understanding of where more evidence is needed, and what kind; appropriate selection of evidence-based approaches; and integrating evidence into action planning.

- 3 Interdisciplinarity: how do we work together effectively?**
Priorities: enabling holistic problem solving and integrated solutions; navigating a plurality of values and approaches.

- 4 Paradigm changes: what are the tipping points for seismic shifts?**
Priorities: ingraining compassion and guardianship; future-proofing ecosystems and embracing survival ecology; challenging power inequalities.

- 5 Language and communication: how can we utilise the power of words?**
Priorities: enabling empathy through our use of language; redefining indigeneity and landscape aesthetics; communicating new paradigms.

5.2. Closing reflections

Several groups highlighted the urgency of the ecological crisis and advocated that as a community of conservationists we need to take more risks. This involves accepting that we will make mistakes; being brave in trying new approaches; and ensuring that when mistakes occur, we report, reflect, learn, and improve. Embracing diverse perspectives and approaches can be powerful, but it requires deliberate effort to build coherence and shared direction, ensuring that diversity enhances rather than hinders collective impact. As a community of different academics and practitioners who care about the renewal of biodiversity, we need diverse approaches to tackle the complex and multivariate ecological and climate crises. Some approaches will work better at different scales and contexts than others; there is no one size fits all. We must strive to be as diverse and adaptable in our perspectives and approaches as the biodiversity we seek to protect, restore, and renew.

This mission could be the beginning of a conversation for identifying new and potentially fruitful collaborations, and perhaps research gaps or future trajectories within and beyond RENEW. Some of the topics and discussions will inform upcoming ExCASES missions.

If you have any other ideas for how we might build on the findings outlined in this report, or have ideas for collaborative opportunities, please use our [ExCASES mission board](#) and [mission submission form](#) as appropriate, or [get in touch](#) with our team directly.

6. Appendix: Workshop Visions

The visioning activity

To create the visions, participants worked in groups carrying out a **quick-fire, collaborative exercise** to see whether they could align around a collective set of goals and identify promising pathways for achieving them. They were also cognisant of possible stumbling blocks and barriers.

Each group explored the **aspirations, challenges and opportunities** of their self-selected theme. There was a **surprising degree of consensus**, albeit at the expense of granular detail. The remaining disagreement pertained mostly to socio-economic and political dimensions. This illustrates the significant differences in how we identify problems and solutions relating to biodiversity renewal across disciplines, sectors and worldviews.

The five visions were brought into our final plenary discussions, where we further reflected on them and **explored connectivity between the themes**.

Please note: the visions summarised below do not necessarily reflect a 'RENEW' position, since not all perspectives were represented.

Aspirations

Decision-makers actively **consider multiple stakeholder perspectives across scales** throughout decision-making processes.

Social and ecological accountability underpins decision-making across all sectors.

A **balanced approach** is taken to what/how data and evidence are accessed and used: natural science, economic data and 'expert' knowledge should be considered alongside social science, ecological evidence, and local knowledge.

Challenges

Decision-making structures and policy are shaped by existing and historical political, economic and legal systems. **How can we urgently disrupt this pattern** to ensure marginalised and unrepresented voices are brought to the fore?

How do we **integrate multiple perspectives and multi-scale dimensions** in an equitable and effective way – for people and nature?

Do we need **more regulation and enforcement** to push businesses to comply?

Opportunities

Using a dual approach to **leverage agency from the bottom-up** (e.g., volunteering, guardianship, direct action), alongside **ambitious, top-down, structural change** (e.g., need for regulation; a fair system for valuing and integrating Rights of Nature; equitable decision-making processes and outcomes; collective action spanning local to global levels to build coordinated and trusted partnerships for urgent change).

Taking a more **long-term approach** in decision-making and planning with funding horizons in mind.

Aspirations

Guardianship is reimagined and culturally ingrained: relational power is redistributed to include people who might previously have felt they were not entitled, or able, to have a relationship with nature.

People are supported and empowered to develop their own sense of what it means to be in **reciprocal, caring relationships** with the natural world.

Heart, emotion, and spirituality are known as important for nurturing meaningful connections with nature. This is reflected in our choice of language when referring to nature, since words have creative power.

Local connections to land are seen and nourished. People cultivate meaning through being of a place, not just *from* a place.

Challenges

Developing a caring relationship with the natural world requires time, which is not equally available due to **financial and material insecurity**.

Leveraging support from large organisations to **support flexible, local scale projects** that allow people to engage and contribute as and when they are able.

Opportunities

Connecting large scale policy initiatives and organisations with smaller scale, local projects.

Influencing the semantics of science communication. Given the importance of emotion for connecting people with the natural world, disciplines such as ecological science should be more accommodating of emotion and relationship in their **use of language** when writing, reporting, and disseminating.

Aspirations

The nutritious food we need is produced from land that is managed in a nature-friendly and low carbon way that **supports inclusive communities** to thrive and enables guardianship.

Findings and recommendations of the **National Food Strategy** are enacted.

An **agro-ecological extension service** has been established that provides advice and guidance to farmers and land managers.

Farmers and land managers are authentically involved in the ongoing **co-creation of solutions**.

Challenges

Re-balancing land use priorities within the farming sector and effectively challenging the power of organisations who lobby for the current status quo.

Navigating tensions when trying to align stakeholders around **a common biodiversity-focussed vision** for food and farming.

The broader considerations and consequences for different people when advocating a **dietary shift**.

Imbalances and fluctuating trends in the **global food system** and the effects of these on policy and priorities in the UK.

Opportunities

Making space for **resistance, challenge and emotion** in decision making processes.

Balancing **incentivisation and agency**, creating bespoke solutions using facilitatory processes.

Aspirations

Biodiversity targets are integrated to create **holistic, functioning ecosystems**.

Biodiversity has a **functional measure** and is valued appropriately.

The holistic function and resilience of ecosystems is **secured for the long term** and conservation continues to **triage species and habitats** that need short-term action.

The role of biodiversity in ecosystem functionality is **reinforced through policy** implementation, for example, the 25-year Environment Plan.

Challenges

A **necessary paradigm shift**: uncertainty about what ecosystem functionality looks like in a rapidly changing climate and the difficulty of communicating this to wider publics.

Building confidence in **embracing uncertainty** amongst conservation practitioners, policy-makers and publics.

Current legislative frameworks may not be able to accommodate a paradigm shift.

Opportunities

Developing **new metrics** to understand and measure the interactions and roles of biodiversity in functional resilience.

Empowerment and communication opportunities around the functional and foundational role of biodiversity in ecosystem resilience.

Aspirations

There is a **co-produced, clear, aspirational vision** for biodiversity renewal around which people with a diversity of views and values are aligning. **Evidence is being generated** to measure progress against this vision.

Different knowledges and approaches are integrated: processes enable **negotiated outcomes** and build in opportunities for **adaptation** in response to emerging evidence.

Pragmatic solutions are supported, e.g. settling for compromised win-wins if they overcome conflict and lead to progress, even if they are not the ideal outcome for any one party.

Challenges

Balancing a survival ecology/future-proofing approach with **the need to protect** particular species, habitats, livelihoods and cultural objectives.

Identifying the right metrics to measure progress, within a broad overarching vision that deliberately accommodates different approaches.

Opportunities

Harnessing the benefits of **plurality** in conservation approaches.

Mediating and resolving conservation conflicts (or making progress despite ongoing conflict) by unifying different stakeholders around an agreed overarching vision.

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ExCASES Mission

The Future of Biodiversity Renewal

ExCASES is a 'solutions generator' designed to tackle issues facing biodiversity renewal that are not covered by RENEW's four core themes. It provides an agile, flexible mechanism to work collaboratively with partners, researchers, and organisations from diverse sectors on focused topics. This cross-cutting theme is run by an interdisciplinary team of researchers based at the National Trust and the University of Exeter.

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